

PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY: THE CASE OF INNOVATION CENTERS

A. Morisson

PAU Department, Mediterranean University of Reggio Calabria, Reggio Calabria, 89124, Italy

Email: arnault.morisson@unirc.it

Abstract: In the late 2000s, new spaces—such as co-working, maker spaces, and co-living spaces—have been emerging in the knowledge-based post-industrial cities. The paper investigates the emergence of innovation centers through the use of public-private partnerships. The research methodology is based on a multiple case-study approach in which three cases were selected: Barcelona Growth Center in Barcelona (Spain), District Hall in Boston (USA), and Edney Innovation Center in Chattanooga (USA). Innovation centers, which consist of widely diverse creative and knowledge-based activities located within the same building, participate in the urban regeneration of downtown areas through the promotion of entrepreneurship. The paper finds that the local governments, which adopt public-private partnerships to create innovation centers, are entrepreneurial and are aligning their actions and visions with those of the entrepreneurs they are trying to attract. For the entrepreneurial local governments, innovation centers are anchor spaces incorporated in a broader vision of making “innovation districts”.

Keywords: Creative City, Innovation Districts, Public-Private Partnership, Knowledge Economy, Urban Regeneration.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the late 2000s, new spaces—such as hacker spaces, maker spaces, Living Labs, Fab Labs, and co-working spaces—have been emerging in concert with the rise of the knowledge and collaborative economy (Botsman & Rogers, 2011; Capdevila, 2015). Civic and innovation-driven entrepreneurs are the main beneficiaries of these new spaces. Entrepreneurs and outsiders are the engine of creative destruction, job creation, economic growth, and the initiators of radical innovations (Christensen, 1997; Kane, 2010; Saxenian, 1994; Schumpeter, 1942). Entrepreneurs have also become, for local governments, the center of attention since the publication by Richard Florida (2002) of *The Rise of the Creative Class*. Chatterji, Glaeser, and Kerr (2013) point out that place-based policies to attract and retain entrepreneurs and startups are positively seen by economists who can be skeptics to the ability of policymakers in picking winners but believe in their ability of picking winning sectors.

Local and regional governments are promoting policies, like the creation of innovation centers, to promote their local entrepreneurial ecosystems. Since 2000, local and regional governments are implementing policies to create innovation districts, which are place-based initiatives that aim to regenerate downtown districts through the promotion of innovative companies and startups, to accelerate their cities’ transitions into the knowledge economy (Katz & Wagner, 2014; Morisson, 2014). Innovation centers are anchor spaces in innovation districts that aim to accelerate the innovation process through promoting collaboration, serendipity, proximity, face-to-face interactions, and the exchange of tacit knowledge between diverse actors through different activities.

The paper investigates the creation of innovation centers through public-private partnerships. Three case studies have been selected: Barcelona Growth Center in Barcelona (Spain), District Hall in Boston (USA), and Edney Innovation Center in Chattanooga (USA). The research conducted for this paper is based on three sources of data: semi-structured interviews, secondary data, and direct observation. Innovation centers are the outcomes of innovative private-public partnerships between entrepreneurial public organizations, entrepreneurial mayors, and private partners (see table 1. for an overview of each case-study). Innovation centers align the vision of local governments with the vision of the entrepreneurial community. As a result, the creation innovation centers through innovative public-private partnerships contribute to reinforce local governments' entrepreneurial spirits.

2. KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY AND PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS

In the 1990s, capitalist countries started to undergo an economic transition towards post-Fordism or knowledge-based economies (Amin, 1994; Drucker, 1998). The knowledge-based economy recognizes the importance of knowledge as the driver of productivity and economic growth, emphasizing the role of information, technology and learning in economic performance (OECD, 1996). In the knowledge economy, technological innovation is essential for economic prosperity. The academic literature provides, both across nations and over time, a solid theoretical background linking technological innovation to the progress of countries, regions, cities, and firms (Fagerberg, 1988; Freeman, 1987; Rosenberg, 1982, 2004; Schumpeter, 1934; Solow, 1957).

In this economic transitions, with the rise of the global economy and the revolutionary nature of ICT, metropolitan areas are the key units to produce technological innovations (Castells, 1989; Florida, Adler, & Mellander, 2017). Indeed, patents and innovations are heavily concentrated in space (Acs & Audretsch, 1988; Carlino, 2001; Jaffe, Trajtenberg, & Henderson, 1993). In introducing the concept of knowledge-based urban development, Knight (1995) correctly recognized that as the economic structure becomes more knowledge-based, the basic nature of urban development changes. Building the “next Silicon Valley” and knowledge-based development initiatives that involve public institutions, universities, and private firms are the epitome of contemporary economic development strategies due to their strong multiplier effect (Etzkowitz, 2015; Moretti, 2012; Sturgeon, 2000).

Metropolitan regions are seen as the most appropriate entity for designing supportive competitive and innovative environments for companies compared to nation states, which in an increasingly borderless world, are increasingly becoming dysfunctional (Cooke, 1997; Krugman, 1995; Ohmae, 1995). In the European Union and the United States, central governments are devolving power and regulatory tasks to subnational institutions, which are becoming more entrepreneurial in order to deliver public services and foster economic growth (Brenner, 2004; Hall & Hubbard, 1996).

One of the tools that local governments are increasingly embracing are public-private partnerships (PPP). Indeed, since the 1990s, public-private partnerships have been used as a key tool of the new public governance for delivering and implementing public policies around the world (Osborne, 2002; Osborne, 2006). In the United States and in the European Union, local and regional governments are taking advantage of private-public partnerships as a way to innovate in times where Federal funds and central governments subsidies are

declining (Sagalyn, 2007). Public-private partnerships are defined as “cooperation of some sort of durability between public and private actors in which they jointly develop products and services and share risks, costs and resources which are connected with these products” (Van Ham & Koppenjan, 2001, p. 598).

In the United States, public-private partnerships have extensively been used in urban development, most notably for the regeneration of Central Business Districts (CBDs) and downtown areas (Harding, 1990; McQuaid, 2000). The limited resources at the disposal of local governments have forced them to take advantage of multiple sources of funding and to work with a wide range of actors, such as the central or federal government, the regional government, the private sector, and the local community, in order to deal with multifaceted local economic development challenges (McQuaid, 2000; Newman & Verpraet, 1999). Lately, local governments are promoting knowledge-based activities out of the desire of generating high-growth activities and high-quality jobs in their cities. Local governments use public-private partnerships to deliver knowledge-based policies and programs, like innovation centers, in very entrepreneurial and innovative manners. Indeed, public-private partnerships can be used in a variety of ways since Mayors and local development offices are only limited by their “imagination” (Lyons & Hamlin, 1991, p. 55).

3. TACIT KNOWLEDGE AND COLLABORATION

Innovation centers are spaces whose objectives are to promote collaboration and face-to-face interactions between diverse organizations, stakeholders, and innovative actors. Innovation centers aim to accelerate the diffusion of tacit knowledge by being open to external and diverse sources of knowledge and to reinforce as a result, the innovative capacities of startups, individuals, and innovative companies located in the building and the district.

In *The Tacit Dimension*, Michael Polanyi (1966) disseminates the concept of tacit knowledge, when he famously observed: “we can know more than we can tell”. Tacit knowledge, in opposition to codified knowledge, refers to the knowledge, ideas, concepts, or insights that individuals possess but cannot be fully expressed. Tacit knowledge is largely transferred through repeated face-to-face, formal and informal, interactions that can only take place at the level of the city or even the district, and is as a result, highly localized. The academic literature widely recognizes the importance of tacit knowledge in the innovation process and in the clustering of high-technology companies (Bathelt, Malmberg, & Maskell, 2004; Gertler, 2003; Howell, 2002; Morgan, 2004, Rodríguez-Pose, & Crescenzi, 2008; Von Hippel, 1994). The general assumption is that by its difficulty of being codified and its dependence on context-specificity, tacit knowledge is more difficult to transfer through distance, and thus, more ‘sticky’ (Von Hippel, 1994). Indeed, while codified knowledge can be disseminated globally at a low cost, due to the process of ubiquitification, tacit knowledge becomes even more critical for competitiveness (Maskell & Malmberg, 1999). Proximity—geographical, cognitive, organizational, social, and institutional—affects the quality of face-to-face interactions and the diffusion of tacit knowledge (Boschma, 2005).

The concepts of the national innovation system (Lundvall, 1992), the sectoral innovation system (Breschi & Malerba, 1997) the regional innovation system (Braczyk, Cooke, & Heidenreich, 1998), the learning region (Florida, 1995; Morgan, 1997), the innovative milieu (Aydalot & Keeble, 1988), and the industrial district (Becattini, 1992), all point out the importance of intraregional networks and interactions in enhancing industrial innovativeness

and regional competitiveness. Collaboration is thus, seen as an important driver in accelerating the innovation process. The interactions between companies and organizations not only in similar economic sectors but also diverse ones can be beneficial to the innovation process thanks to knowledge spillovers (Jacobs, 1969). The concept of open innovation acknowledges the importance of inflows and outflows of ideas and tacit knowledge in the process of innovation (Chesbrough, 2003). Interactions and cooperation between university-industry-government and the civil society are necessary preconditions for regional competitiveness in the context of the knowledge economy (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009; Leydesdorff & Etzkowitz, 1996).

4. METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is based on a qualitative multiple case-study approach, using primary and secondary data. The author uses case studies “out of the desire to understand complex social phenomena” (Yin, 1994, p. 4). Indeed, this research investigates in an exploratory manner a contemporary phenomenon in which the researcher has no control on the actual phenomenon (Eisenhardt, 1989). Moreover, the investigation of public-private partnerships for the creation of innovation centers has not been fully examined. A qualitative approach is as a result, the most appropriate method (Eisenhardt, 1989). The researcher uses a comparative exploratory multiple case-study approach in order to generalize findings on the new concept studied. The three innovation centers selected are located in three different cities in developed countries, they are: Barcelona Growth Center in Barcelona (Spain), District Hall in Boston (USA), and Edney Innovation Center in Chattanooga (USA).

The research conducted for this paper is based on three sources of data: semi-structured interviews, secondary data, and direct observation. The semi-structured interviews were conducted for each innovation center in person and over the phone with the key stakeholders who have directly participated in the innovation center’s design and/or implementation. In total, seven interviews were conducted: three interviews for Barcelona Growth Center, two interviews for District Hall, and two interviews for Edney Innovation Center. The persons interviewed were: the District Hall’s director, Chattanooga’s strategic planner, 22@ Barcelona’s employees and director, university professors, and the City of Boston Mayor’s Office. The stakeholders were selected according to their strong knowledge and diverse perspectives on the phenomena studied (Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007). The secondary data that were used for the research are, but were not limited to: innovation centers’ websites, namely District Hall, Edney Innovation Center, and 22@ Barcelona; the municipal organizations’ websites, namely Boston Redevelopment Authority, The Enterprise Center, and 22@ Barcelona; the government websites of the City of Barcelona, Boston, and Chattanooga; real-estate developers’ websites such as WS Development, Consorci de la Zona Franca de Barcelona; articles in news websites, newspapers, and magazines such as nooga.com, New York Times, Boston Globe, La Vanguardia, and Boston.com; annual reports from The Enterprise Center, and official planning documents from 22@ Barcelona and Boston Redevelopment Authority. The direct observations involved non-participatory observations in each of the innovation center. In total, the researcher conducted about 6 hours of formal and informal observations. The data were then, converged in a triangulating fashion in order to “assure that the right information and interpretations have been obtained” (Stake, 2013, p. 36).

5. CASE-STUDIES

5.1 Barcelona Growth Center - Barcelona, Spain

The Barcelona Growth Center, previously known as the MediaTic building, is at the center of the innovation district—22@ Barcelona. In 2000, under Mayor Joan Clos, the City of Barcelona launched the innovation district, 22@ Barcelona, in order to accelerate the city's transition into the knowledge economy (Barceló & Oliva, 2002; Trullén, 2001). The innovation district is located in the district of Poblenou, a former industrial district, used to be known as the “Manchester of Catalonia” (López, Romani, Sagarra, & Piqué, 2011). The objectives of 22@ Barcelona were: to redevelop the district of Poblenou, to promote industries in five clusters—media, ICT, medical technologies, energy, and design—and to accelerate Barcelona's transition into the knowledge economy (Trullén, 2001; López et al., 2011). A municipal company, 22 ARROBA BCN S.A., was created by Mayor Joan Clos with the sole purpose to transform the Poblenou district into an innovation district

The Barcelona Growth Center is a nine-story and 15,000-square-meter building located in the center of the district—22@ Barcelona . The users and activities of the innovation center are: a business support office; the Cibernàrium, a public-sponsored program that offers training for professionals, students, and residents; the Mobile StartUp Barcelona, a co-working space for entrepreneurs and startup accelerators; the Mobile World Capital Barcelona, a public organization that organizes the Mobile World Congress in Barcelona; the GSMA, which is the global trade association for mobile phone operators, manufacturers and suppliers; Accenture Mobile Knowledge; Deloitte; the Technological Circle of Catalonia (CTecno), a foundation that unites companies and professionals in the Information and Communications Technology sector; Softonic, a software company; previous tenants included the Open University of Catalonia; the Internet Interdisciplinary Institute (IN3); and an eLearning Center. The Barcelona Growth Center is today a hub and meeting point for entrepreneurs, accelerators, public institutions, students, and private companies in the sectors of ICT and Media (Barcelona Activa, 2012).

The Barcelona Growth Center was opened in 2010 to serve as the center for 22@ Barcelona's Media and ICT clusters (Barceló & Guillot, 2013). The public-private partnership that led to the creation of the innovation center followed a complex two-step process. In the first step, the land, which was privately-owned, was transferred to the municipal company, 22 ARROBA BCN S.A., due to the compulsory land transfer in the innovation district. In 22@ Barcelona, the zoning laws were modified in 2000 to give an incentive for real estate developers to build more by providing them additional zoning rights under certain conditions. First, real-estate developers were obliged to dedicate twenty percent of the total built area to “@” activities, which are knowledge-based activities as defined by the OECD (Barceló & Guillot, 2013; Barcelona, 2000). Second, real estate developers had to transfer 30 percent of the built land to 22 ARROBA BCN S.A. (Barceló & Guillot, 2013; Barcelona, 2000). The municipal company was then allocating the land to provide parks, public housing, and “7@ amenities” like the Barcelona Growth Center, which are spaces to accommodate knowledge activities and diffuse new technologies (Barcelona, 2000). In the second step, a joint-venture was created between the municipal company, 22 ARROBA BCN S.A., and a quasi-public real estate developer, the Consorci of Zona Franca de Barcelona, in order to build “7@ amenities” on the land transferred by a private real estate developer to the municipal company. The joint-venture negotiated to determine the architectural aspects, the activities, and uses of the building. It was agreed that the Consorci of Zona Franca de Barcelona would finance the construction of the Barcelona Growth Center and would have the right to use the

building for a period of 70 years before transferring back the right to use the building to the city. The city would have the right to use three floors of the building to promote knowledge activities for the same period of 70 years.

In Barcelona, the public-private partnership that led to the creation of the innovation center consisted of a joint-venture and negotiations between 22 ARROBA BCN S.A. and the Consorci de Zona Franca de Barcelona. The municipal company, 22 ARROBA BCN S.A., consisted of public entrepreneurs who had a certain degree of autonomy and flexibility to form innovative public-private partnerships in order to transform the district into an innovation district. The local government in Barcelona through its entrepreneurial spinoff, 22 ARROBA BCN S.A., was using the codes of the entrepreneur community to create a space dedicated to entrepreneurship and innovative activities.

5.2 District Hall - Boston, United States

The District Hall is a flagship program at the center of Mayor Menino's vision to build an innovation district in the South Boston waterfront, a former industrial district in Boston. Boston's Innovation District was the outcome of a negotiation between real-estate companies and the City of Boston (BRA, 2010). The Boston Redevelopment Authority (BRA) negotiated with Gale International, Morgan Stanley, and W/S Development Associates, to include, in their plans for developing the Seaport Square, a real estate megaproject, a range of public benefits consisting of "Innovation Uses", civic and cultural spaces (BRA, 2010). The Innovation Uses include: laboratories, small business incubators, public event spaces for exhibitions, rooftop gardens, the District Hall, retail businesses, hotels, innovation transportation and energy, and public, common, or shared spaces within innovation/workforce housing (BRA, 2010).

The District Hall is a single-story and 1,115-square-meter located in the heart of Boston's Innovation District. The innovation center claims to be "the world's first free-standing public innovation center and a dedicated civic space where the innovation community can gather and exchange ideas" (www.districthallboston.org). The activities located in the innovation center are: a restaurant, a coffee shop; a lounge, which is completely open to the public; a large and flexible conference room; and 3 flexible meeting rooms. The users of the innovation center are: startups, entrepreneurs, students, nonprofit organizations, local associations, local residents, and corporate companies.

The District Hall was opened in 2013 to serve as an anchor institution that contributes to the visibility of Boston's Innovation District. The District Hall was created as a public benefit through Boston's incentive zoning rights. In Boston, the Boston Redevelopment Authority, Boston's urban planning department, which is supervised by the Mayor's office, confers property rights, such as additional density, to real estate developers in exchange for public benefits to the community. The innovation center is the outcome of a yearlong negotiation between real estate companies that asked for additional density in the Seaport Square's project, the largest real estate development in Boston's history, and the Boston Redevelopment Authority that requested for specific public benefits, namely innovation uses (BRA, 2010). In the public-private partnership, the real estate companies built the District Hall and granted a lease to Boston Redevelopment Authority for \$1 per year for a minimum period of 5 years with renewable rights for an additional period of 5 years (BRA, 2010). The Boston Redevelopment Authority transferred the right to use the building to a nonprofit

organization, Venture Café Foundation, which was created in 2010 by Timothy Rowe, the founder of the Cambridge Innovation Center in Kendall Square. In exchange, the Venture Café Foundation agrees to organize programming and events in the innovation center. The Boston Redevelopment Authority evaluates on a quarterly basis the activities of the innovation center. The funding to operate the innovation center comes from corporate sponsors, corporate events, and the rents given by a restaurant and a coffee shop located in the building that are operated by the Briar Group. Additionally, Venture Café Foundation doesn't pay taxes to the City of Boston for innovation-related events and activities.

In Boston, the public-private partnership that led to the creation of the innovation center consisted of a yearlong negotiation between Boston Redevelopment Authority and real estate developers. The Boston Redevelopment Authority then partnered with a nonprofit organization, which is funded through the rents given by the restaurant and coffee shop located in the building, in order to run events and operate the innovation center. The Mayor's office used multidimensional and creative partnerships in order to spur the creation of its innovation center.

5.3 Edney Innovation Center - Chattanooga, United States

Chattanooga is a mid-sized city located in Tennessee in the United States. Since the 1970s, Chattanooga has reinvented itself from being "America's Dirtiest City" into becoming an emerging innovation hub (Motoyama, Fetsch, Jackson, & Wiens, 2016). The city has built upon its capacity to generate successful public-private partnerships with philanthropic foundations, entrepreneurs, and public organizations, to redevelop its waterfront and its Central Business District. In 2010, the Electricity Power Board (EPB), a public-owned utility company owned by the City of Chattanooga, launched the fastest fiber-optic Internet network in the United States, dubbed as the "Gig", that provided residents with one gigabit speed Internet (Motoyama et al., 2016).

In 2015, Mayor Berke announced the creation of an innovation district and an innovation center in downtown Chattanooga that was to be piloted by the Enterprise Center. The Enterprise Center is a nonprofit public-private partnership that focus on promoting the innovation economy in Chattanooga. The Enterprise Center was created in 2014 to build upon the the opportunities that could be leveraged from the Gig upon the recommendations of the Chattanooga Forward Gig, Entrepreneurship and Technology Task Force Report.

The Edney Innovation Center is a 10-story and 8,360-square-meter building located in the heart of Chattanooga's innovation district. The tenants of the innovation center are: CO.LAB, a nonprofit startup accelerator; Tech Town, a technology learning center; Society of Work, a co-working space; private companies, and the Enterprise Center. The building includes a community space open to the public, a rooftop gathering space, and proximately a restaurant, a coffee shop, and an open space on the ground floor. The users of the building are: entrepreneurs, community and nonprofit organizations, private companies, and students. The Enterprise Center, which is located on the fifth floor, organizes networking events, workshops, and public and private events in its community space. The innovation center aims to become the catalyst connector for Chattanooga's entrepreneurial ecosystem.

The Edney Innovation Center was opened in late 2015 and is at the center of Mayor's Berke's vision to establish an innovation district in Chattanooga. The creation of the innovation center

was the outcome of negotiations between a wide range of different actors. The building was owned by the Tennessee Valley Authority (TVA), a Federally-owned utility agency. Mayor Berke and Harold DePriest, the CEO of the Electricity Power Board, facilitated the purchase of the building to the Enterprise Center for favorable terms due to EPB's and the City of Chattanooga's historical partnerships with TVA on the condition that the building be used as an innovation center (The Enterprise Center, 2015). The Mayor's office funded the inspection of the building before the purchase by the Enterprise Center. In early 2015, the Enterprise Center issued a *Request for Proposal* (RFP) in order to identify a real estate developer to retrofit the building into an innovation center (The Enterprise Center, 2015). The *Request of Proposal* stated that Co.Lab was to lease the eastern section of the first floor of the building and the Enterprise Center was to lease the western section of the first floor and an additional floor at market rate for a period of 5 years, with a 5 year option (The Enterprise Center, 2015). Co.Lab and the Enterprise Center would assist the real estate developer in the creation and programming of the innovation center. The real estate developer selected was to become a full partner in supporting the innovation center's vision by selecting tenants and promoting uses relevant for the knowledge economy (The Enterprise Center, 2015). In 2015, a local real estate developer, DEW Edney LLC, was selected to retrofit the building (Motoyama et al., 2016).

In Chattanooga, the Enterprise Center played the role of coordinating, planning, and implementing the Mayor's vision of an innovation center in the city. The Enterprise Center is a nonprofit public-private partnership that receives its funding from the City of Chattanooga, Federal grants, foundations, and private companies (The Enterprise Center, 2016). The Enterprise Center is to some extent, the entrepreneurial arm of the Mayor's office. The public-private partnership that led to the creation of the innovation center consisted of a *Request for Proposal* and negotiations between the Enterprise Center and the local real estate developer, Dew Edney LLC.

6. DISCUSSION

Innovation centers are being created in diverse cities around the world to accommodate entrepreneurs and knowledge workers. While innovation centers are often built with private funds by entrepreneurs, this paper shows that innovation centers can also be the outcome of public-private partnerships in which local governments act as public entrepreneurs. Innovation centers are innovation districts' anchor institutions that participate in knowledge-based development and the urban regeneration of previously industrial or manufacturing urban districts. Local governments that build innovation centers aim to provide their local entrepreneurial ecosystems with the required informal infrastructures to facilitate face-to-face interactions, collaboration, and the exchange of tacit knowledge in order to accelerate the process of innovation. As Peter Hall (1998) showed, innovative city-regions not only have few, if not any, barriers to the diffusion of innovations, but have also strong but informal structures for exchanges of ideas and knowledge. Local policymakers are more and more keen to embrace innovation policies for their cities. Innovation centers are not however, a "one-size-fits-all" innovation policy. Indeed, innovation centers participate in the making of an innovation district and as a result, should only be promoted when an existing innovation ecosystem already or potentially exists.

Table 1. Overview of the Case-Studies

	Innovation Centers		
Name	Edney Innovation Center	District Hall	Barcelona Growth Center
Location	Chattanooga-Tennessee-USA	Boston-Massachusetts-USA	Barcelona-Spain
Creation Date	2015	2013	2010
Type of Partnership	Public-Private Partnership - RFP-Legal Agreement	Public-Private Partnership - Public Benefit	Public-Private Partnership - Joint Venture
Lead Coordinating Organization	The Enterprise Center	Boston Redevelopment Authority	22 ARROBA BCN S.A.
Floor Area	8,360 Square Meters	1,115 Square Meters	15,000 Square Meters
Purpose	Anchor space for Chattanooga's Innovation District	Anchor space for Boston's Innovation District	Anchor space for 22@ Barcelona's Media and ICT clusters
Key Actors	The Enterprise Center; The Mayor's Office; Private Foundations; Real Estate Developer; Tennessee Valley Authority	The Boston Redevelopment Authority; The Mayor's Office; Real Estate Developers; The Venture Foundation; Briar Group	22 ARROBA BCN S.A.; The Mayor's Office; Barcelona Activa; Consorci Zona Franca de Barcelona
Activities in the Innovation Center	Coffee Shop (opening soon), Restaurant (opening soon), Co-Working Spaces, Accelerators, Collision Space, Office Space, Public and Private Events	Coffee Shop, Restaurant, Conference Rooms, Meeting Rooms, Open Co-working Spaces, Public and Private Events	Conference Rooms, Co-Working Spaces, Accelerators, Cibernarium Training Center, Business Support Office, Office Spaces, Parking, Public and Private Events

6. CONCLUSIONS

The paper finds that an innovation center can be the outcome of creative and innovative private-public partnerships as it was the case in Barcelona, Boston, and Chattanooga. In each case-study, the local government had a strong direct or indirect leadership role in negotiating or providing resources and incentives to build their innovation centers. More importantly, Mayors were critical in communicating their visions for the creation an innovation center to a wide range of potential partners. Mayors took advantage of or created entrepreneurial organizations, such as 22 ARROBA BCN S.A. in Barcelona, the Boston Redevelopment Authority in Boston, and the Enterprise Center in Chattanooga, in order to gain in flexibility and to remove bureaucratic processes, and thus, facilitated the implementation of their entrepreneurial visions.

Entrepreneurial mayors support the creation of entrepreneurial organizations to endorse public-private partnerships in order to rapidly and efficiently create innovation centers and accelerate their cities' transition into the knowledge-based economy. In endorsing creative and innovative public-private partnerships, local governments are adopting the codes of the entrepreneurial community. In doing so, this new wave of public entrepreneurialism enhances the legitimacy and signals the local governments' commitment to improving their local innovation ecosystems to the entrepreneurial community. The new wave of entrepreneurial mayors and public organizations participate in the current debate of the supposedly superior local government's advantages in finding innovation solutions to local economic development challenges (Pike, Rodríguez-Pose, & Tomaney, 2017). The paper has however, a limited scope since it deals with the creation of innovation centers through public-private

partnerships in developed and relatively large cities with efficient public institutions, and as a result, offers little relevance to urban policymakers in lower-income countries.

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